

1 **Supplementary Figure Legends**

2 **Supplementary Figure 1.** Synergy maps of dose response assays of Fulv combination
3 **(A)** and Palb combination **(B)** with NAMPTi, ATR, BOA, ACSI and DG using four
4 different methods; ZIP, Bliss, Loewe, HSA. Heatmaps of dose response assays of Fulv
5 combination **(C)** and Palb combination **(D)** groups. Synergy and heat maps were
6 prepared using <https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/> web site.

7 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Isobolograms for dose response assays of Fulv combination
8 **(A)**, Palb combination **(B)** and Tamoxifen combination **(C)** with NAMPTi, ATR, BOA,
9 ACSI and DG. . Synergy maps of dose response assays of Tamoxifen combination **(D)**
10 with NAMPTi, ATR, BOA, ACSI and DG using four different methods; ZIP, Bliss, Loewe,
11 HSA. Synergy and heat maps were prepared using <https://synergyfinder.fimm.fi/> web
12 site.

13 **Supplementary Figure 3. (A)** IVIS images for tumor burden in mice injected with MCF7
14 ESR1 Y537S cells and treated with Veh, Fulv, Palb and Fulv+Palb. **(B)** Quantification of
15 signal from **(A)**. **(C)** Body weight change in Fulv and Palb groups during treatment. **(D)**
16 Food consumption in Fulv and Palb groups during treatment.

17 **Supplementary Figure 4.** Normalized enrichment score comparison of Fulv vs
18 Fulv+Palb and Fulv+Palb vs Fulv+NAMPTi groups for gene sets involved in Breast
19 Cancer, Metastasis and Metabolism. Analysis done using GSEA 4.3.1.

20 **Supplementary Figure 5. (A)** Heatmap of combination groups as single values. **(B)**
21 Heatmap of Fulv groups as single values.

22 **Supplementary Table 1.** GSEA analysis of genes in each cluster.

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